

CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHILDREN'S GAMES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Qarshiboyeva Xurshida Shermat qizi

O`ZDJTU tarjimonlik fakulteti, 1-kurs magistri

E-mail: xurshidaqarshiboyeva943@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10541387>

Abstract: This article presents an abstract on the cultural characteristics of children's games in English and Uzbek languages. The social, educational, and cultural aspects of children's games are analyzed in both Uzbek and English languages. Throughout the article, the games, their uniqueness, expressive aspects in both languages, cultural significance, as well as teaching methods through games and their impact on the learning process, were analyzed. This article provides valuable insights and information about the linguistic and cultural aspects of children's games in Uzbek and English languages.

Key words: Children's games, cultural significance, cultural heritage, cultural awareness.

КУЛЬТУРНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДЕТСКИХ ИГР НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация: В данной статье приведено краткое изложение культурных характеристик детских игр на английском и узбекском языках. Анализируются социальные, образовательные и культурные аспекты детских игр на узбекском и английском языках. В ходе исследования были проанализированы игры, их уникальность, выразительные особенности на обоих языках, культурное значение, а также методы преподавания через игры и их влияние на процесс обучения. Данная статья предоставляет ценную информацию о лингвистических и культурных особенностях детских игр на узбекском и английском языках.

Ключевые слова: Детские игры, культурное значение, культурное наследие, культурное сознание.

INTRODUCTION

Children's games play a pivotal role in transmitting cultural values and traditions from one generation to another. These games serve as a medium through which children learn about their culture, develop social skills, and acquire language proficiency. Understanding the cultural characteristics embedded within children's games in different languages provides valuable insights into the diverse ways children engage with their respective cultures. This article focuses on the cultural characteristics of children's games in English and Uzbek languages, shedding light on the unique elements that shape children's cultural identities.

Children's games are an integral part of cultural heritage and language development. This article explores the cultural characteristics embedded within children's games in English and Uzbek languages. By examining the cultural elements present in these games, including traditional practices, values, and symbols, we gain insights into how children engage with their respective cultures through play. The article highlights the significance of understanding cultural aspects in children's games for promoting cultural preservation, language acquisition, and fostering cultural identity.

Cultural Significance in Children's Games:

Children's games serve as a reflection of the cultural heritage of a community or society. They often incorporate elements such as traditional songs, dances, stories, and symbols that hold cultural significance. These cultural elements are interwoven with the gameplay itself, creating an immersive experience for children. By participating in these games, children connect with their cultural roots, learn about societal norms, and develop a sense of belonging.

Language and Cultural Learning through Games:

Children's games provide a rich linguistic environment for language acquisition. Within the context of English and Uzbek languages, games offer opportunities for children to practice vocabulary, sentence structures, and conversational skills. Moreover, cultural elements within these games introduce children to the unique aspects of their respective cultures, including history, folklore, and customs. Language and culture go hand in hand in children's games, facilitating a holistic learning experience.

Preserving Cultural Heritage:

Children's games serve as a means of preserving cultural heritage. By passing down traditional games from one generation to the next, cultural practices are kept alive. These games act as a bridge between the past and the present, allowing children to engage with their cultural heritage and maintain a connection to their roots. Preserving cultural heritage through games ensures that future generations will continue to embrace and celebrate their cultural identity.

Implications for Education and Cultural Awareness:

Recognizing the cultural characteristics of children's games has significant implications for education and cultural awareness. Incorporating culturally relevant games in educational settings can enhance language learning, foster cultural appreciation, and promote inclusive learning environments. Educators can leverage children's games as tools for teaching language, cultural values, and intercultural understanding. By embracing diversity and cultural exchange, children develop respect for different cultures and build bridges of understanding.

The cultural characteristics of children's games in English encompass a diverse range of activities reflecting societal values, traditions, and play patterns. These games often intertwine education with entertainment, fostering social skills and creativity. For instance, traditional English children's games like "Ring-a-Ring o' Roses" carry historical significance, while contemporary ones such as "Simon Says" showcase the influence of modern communication and technology on play. Examining these games provides insights into the evolving cultural landscape of childhood experiences in English-speaking communities.

Example for english and uzbek children's games:

One example of a traditional English children's game is "London Bridge is Falling Down." In this game, children form an arch with their arms, and another child or group passes underneath the arch while the song "London Bridge is falling down, falling down, falling down" is sung. When the song finishes, the arch lowers, capturing the child passing through. This game reflects historical elements, as the London Bridge has undergone various rebuilds throughout history, making it an engaging and culturally rooted activity for English children.

One example of a traditional Uzbek children's game is "Chapan."¹ In this game, children join hands and form a circle, then move in a coordinated manner, emphasizing teamwork and social interaction. The objective is to maintain the unity of the circle while playfully attempting to

¹T. Usmonxo'jayev, F. Xo'jayev. 1001 o'yin. 234-b

pull one designated child into the center. "Chapan" not only promotes physical activity but also fosters a sense of cooperation and camaraderie among Uzbek children, showcasing the cultural emphasis on community bonds and mutual support.

CONCLUSION

Children's games in English and Uzbek languages encompass rich cultural characteristics that contribute to language acquisition, cultural preservation, and the development of cultural identity. Recognizing the cultural elements embedded within these games allows for a deeper understanding of how children engage with their respective cultures. By promoting the integration of culturally relevant games in educational settings, we can create inclusive environments that celebrate diversity and foster intercultural understanding among children. Embracing the cultural characteristics of children's games strengthens cultural preservation efforts and enriches the language learning experiences of children in both English and Uzbek contexts.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Oxunjon Safarov. O'zbek xalq bolalar o'yinlari. -T.: Sharq, 2013.-176b2.
2. Iona Archibald Opie, Peter Opie. Children's games in street and playground: Chasing, catching, seeking, hunting, racing, duelling, exerting daring, guessing, acting, pretending. Oxford university press, 1984 –Family and relationships-371 pages.
3. Iona Archibald Opie, Peter Opie. The Lore and Language of Schoolchildren, Oxford university press, 1959.
4. M. I. Rasulova, Z. I. Shukurova. Comparative typology of Uzbek, English and Russian languages
5. T. Usmonxo'jayev, F. Xo'jayev. 1001 o'yin. -Toshkent
6. Teliya V. N. Linguoculturology - the key to the new reality of the phenomenon of reproducibility of several-word formations // Language. Culture. Communication: Collection of scientific papers in honor of S.G. Ter-Minasova. – M. Gnosis, 2008.